

Oxidation of oxime derivative of friedelin with hydrogen peroxide in presence of selenium dioxide in *tert*-butanol and antimicrobial activity of the isolated compounds

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Abstract : Oxime derivative (1a) of friedelin (1) on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide and selenium dioxide in tertiary butanol furnishes an ϵ -lactone, friedelolactone (2) and 2,3-*seco*-friedelonic acid (3). The structures of these compounds have been fully established on the basis of spectral data (IR, MS, PMR, and ^{13}C NMR). Antimicrobial activity of the compounds were also investigated and the results are reported herein.

Keywords : Triterpene, oxime, friedelin, antimicrobial.

Introduction

Transformative reactions on triterpenoids of lupane and friedelin skeleton using a host of oxidizing and reducing agents have already been reported from our laboratory¹⁻⁶. Although several studies on oxidation of triterpenoids⁷⁻¹⁰ with hydrogen peroxide and selenium dioxide have been reported but no communication on the study of the oxime derivative of triterpenoid ketones with this reagent has been investigated so far. In view of that and in order to examine the nature of the products formed during the oxidation of oxime derivatives of 3-ketotriterpenoids of friedelin skeleton, the oxidation of keto oximes of friedelin with hydrogen peroxide and selenium dioxide has been undertaken. The characterisation of the products (A-B) along with their evaluated biological activity are presented in this paper.

Oxime derivative **1a** of friedelin (1) in tertiary butanol was refluxed with selenium dioxide and hydrogen peroxide. The residue obtained after recovery of solvent by distillation was extracted with ether and separated into neutral and acid parts by usual method.

The neutral part of the reaction product of **1a** furnished compound **A** which was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH, m.p. 278 °C. It analysed for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$; MS m/z 442 (M^+). Its IR spectrum showed a peak at 1740 cm^{-1}

which was due to ϵ -lactone moiety. The presence of ϵ -lactone moiety was supported by appearance of a lactonic proton (CO-O-CH-CH_3) at δ 4.22 as ABq (J 6.3, 12.8 Hz) in its PMR spectrum, the appearance of multiplet at 2.6 (2H) was due to the presence of methylene protons adjacent to the carbonyl group ($-\text{O-CO-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2-$). On the basis of the above spectral data, compound **A** has been identified as friedelolactone¹¹ (**2**).

Esterification of the acid part with diazomethane followed by chromatography yielded a single product (**B**) which was further purified by crystallisation from chloroform-methanol, m.p. 169–170 °C. The compound **B** was analyzed for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_4$ (M^+ , 502). Its IR spectrum was indicative of the presence of carbomethoxy group at 1750 cm^{-1} . The ester was found to be identical with methyl 2,3-*seco*-friedelionate^{9,12} (**3a**) by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-IR and co-TLC) and study of its spectral data. Hence the corresponding acid is 2,3-*seco*-friedelonic acid^{9,13} (**3**).

Results and discussion

Retention of nitrogen during the reaction of the triterpenoid oximes with SeO_2 is reported in the literature¹⁴. In the present case the addition of H_2O_2 has been found to change the nature of products free of nitrogen. This implies that the oxime **1a** first oxidized by H_2O_2 in presence of SeO_2 to the respective ketones **1** which undergo usual oxidation reaction to furnish compounds **A-B**. The structures of both the compounds were established based on their spectral data (IR, UV, and NMR) and also by comparison with the already reported data^{9,11,12}. All the compounds were evaluated for their antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum benzene used had b.p. 60-80 °C. PMR spectra (Chemical shifts in δ ppm; TMS as internal standard) and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on Bruker WH-400 and Bruker WH-270 with DEPT programme; IR spectra in nujol in Pye Unicem-300 spectrometer and mass spectra on a Varian MAT 711 at 70 eV. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60-120 mesh, BDH). TLC was performed on chromatoplate of silica gel G (Glaxo and BDH) and the spots were located by exposing to iodine chamber.

Oxidation of oxime (**1a**) :

A solution of the oxime derivative (**1a**, 0.5 g) in tertiary butanol (100 ml) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (0.5 g) and hydrogen peroxide (20 mL, 25%) for 60 h. The completion of the reaction was indicated by deposition of black selenium metal. After recovery of the solvent by distillation, the residue was extracted with ether and separated into neutral and acid parts by usual method. The neutral part was chromatographed over silica gel column. The acid part was esterified with diazomethane and the reaction product chromatographed over silica gel column. Elution of the column with solvents of increasing polarities was performed and residue of the same polarity and same R_f value in TLC were combined together and purified by crystallizations.

Oxidation products of friedelin oxime (**1a**) :

Friedelo lactone **2** :

The neutral part of the reaction product of **1a** was

chromatographed and elution with petrol : benzene (3 : 2) furnished a single compound **A** (0.15 g) which was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH to afford white solid, m.p. 278 °C; IR : 1740 cm^{-1} (ϵ -lactone); PMR : δ 0.82, 0.88, 0.94, 1.00, 1.18, 1.22 (21H, 7s, $7 \times \text{tert-CH}_3$), 0.99 (3H, d, J 6.5 Hz, H-C- CH_3), 2.6 (2H, m, -O- CH_2 -CH-), 4.22 (1H, ABq, J 6.3, 12.8 Hz, -CO-O-CH- CH_3); ^{13}C NMR : 15.6 (t, C-1), 34.4 (t, C-2), 175.8 (s, C-3), 84.5 (d, C-4), 40.8 (s, C-5), 38.4 (t, C-6), 18.0 (t, C-7), 52.7 (d, C-8), 38.2 (s, C-9), 64.0 (d, C-10), 35.4 (t, C-11), 30.6 (t, C-12), 39.3 (s, C-13), 38.4 (s, C-14), 32.3 (t, C-15), 35.9 (t, C-16), 30.0 (s, C-17), 42.7 (d, C-18), 35.3 (t, C-19), 28.1 (s, C-20), 32.7 (t, C-21), 39.2 (t, C-22), 13.4 (q, C-23), 16.2 (q, C-24), 17.9 (q, C-25), 20.2 (q, C-26), 18.6 (q, C-27), 32.2 (q, C-28), 31.7 (q, C-29), 35.0 (q, C-30); MS : m/z 442 [M^+], 427, 398, 383, 274, 245, 219, 218, 206, 205, 191, 177, 163, 149, 123, 109, 107, 95 (base) [Found : C, 81.2; H, 11.0. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.39; H, 11.38%]. The compound was found to be identical with an authentic sample of friedelolactone **2** on comparison of its m.m.p., co-TLC and co-IR.

Methyl ester (**3a**) of 2,3-*seco*-friedelononic acid **3** :

Compound **B** [0.3 g, eluted by petrol : benzene (2 : 3)] was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH to furnish white crystals, m.p. 69-70 °C; IR : 1750 cm^{-1} (-COOMe); MS : m/z 502 [M^+], 487, 471, 455, 442, 429, 415 (base peak), 355, 301, 273, 245, 219, 205 and 191 [Found : C, 76.2; H, 10.5. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_4$: C, 76.45; H, 10.83%]. Mixed m.p., co-TLC and co-IR of compound **B**, with an authentic sample of methyl 2,3-*seco*-friedelonate **3a** confirmed its identity.

Antimicrobial activity :

Although the compounds (**1-3a**), do not show any significant phytotoxicity when tested on a number of specimens (Table 3) but showed prominent antimicrobial activities against the tested fungal and bacterial pathogens as evidenced from the Tables 1 and 2. Compound **2** and **3a** showed better activity against all the microorganisms compare to the parent natural product, friedelin (**1**) and their activity is found comparable to that of Ampicillin against *E. coli* and *Enterobactor*. The activity of compound **2** and **3a** was nearly comparable to that of Bavistan, when tested against *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* and

Table 1. MICs of **1** to **3a** against different bacteria

Compds.	MIC in µg/ml against different bacterial strains			
	EC	BS	SA	EB
1	100	130	150	150
2	150	100	200	100
3a	130	< 150	100	100
Ampicillin	128	64	64	128

BS – *Bacillus subtilis*, EC – *Escherichia coli*, SA – *Staphylococcus aureus*, EB – *Enterobacter*.
MIC – Minimum inhibitory concentration.

Table 2. MICs of **1** to **3a** against different fungal strains

Compds.	MIC in µg/ml against different fungal strains				
	CG	FE	CE	AA	CC
1	5.00	20.0	35.0	20.0	39.0
2	4.87	19.5	40.0	19.5	39.0
3a	< 5.0	20.0	40.0	10.0	< 5.0
Bavistan	3.50	3.50	3.70	4.00	4.20

CG – *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, FE – *Fusarium equisiti*, CE – *Curvularia eragrostidis*, AA – *Alternaria alternata*, CC – *Colletotrichum camelliae*.

Table 3. Phytotoxicity of the compounds based on the length (in cm) of roots after 7 days

Compds.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Rice	Wheat	Pea
		Control	0.5	1.10
1	100	0.5	11.2	1.53
	250	0.5	1.13	1.53
	500	0.5	1.12	1.53
2	100	0.5	1.21	1.62
	250	0.5	1.22	1.64
	500	0.5	1.25	1.65
3a	100	0.5	1.09	1.65
	250	0.5	1.09	1.64
	500	0.5	1.11	1.63

Colletotrichum camelliae. Finally it can be concluded that the present study will be extremely helpful to enrich the present knowledge about triterpenoids of friedelin skeleton and also help the researchers to develop newer generation of drugs based on such information about triterpenoids of friedelin skeleton.

General procedure :

In the present study, five different fungal pathogens (*Colletotrichum camelliae*, *Fusarium equisiti*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Curvularia eragrostidis* and *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*) were used for *in vitro* antifungal as-

say^{15,16}. Antibacterial assay were performed against four bacterial pathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter*). Suitable strains of these organisms were procured from the microbiology laboratory of our institute. MICs (Minimum inhibitory concentration) of the triterpenoids against bacterial and fungal pathogens have been presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The antifungal and antibacterial media used are as follows. For nutrient agar 28 g of media (HiMedia) was suspended in 1000 ml of distilled water according to the manufacturer's protocol. It was boiled to dissolve the medium completely at sterilized by autoclaving at 15 lbs pressure (121 °C for 15 min). The nutrient agar contained peptic digest of animal tissue (5 g), sodium chloride (5 g), beef extract (1.5 g), yeast extract (1.5 g), agar (15 g) and dissolved water (1000 ml). pH was adjusted to 7.2. For preparation of PDA (potato-dextrose-agar) peeled potato was cut into small pieces and boiled in required volume of dissolved water. The mixture was filtered through muslin cloth and the extract was mixed with dextrose and agar. The resultant mixture was heated in order to dissolve. Finally the media was sterilized at 15 lbs (121 °C for 15 min). Composition of the media was peeled potato (400 g), dextrose (20 g), agar (20 g) and dissolved water (1000 ml). pH was adjusted to 6.0. DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) was used as solvent to prepare different concentrations of the triterpenoids. Solvent control (DMSO) was also maintained throughout the experiment. All experiments were performed in petridishes and were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. The required media (either PDA or NA) was poured in a petridish and allowed for solidification. After solidification wells or cups were made by inserting a cork borer in the media. The numbers of wells were made according to the requirement of the experiment. Fungal spores were suspended on the PDA media before well or cup formation. Test solution (100 µL/well) was poured in the well or cup. We compared the antifungal activities of these compounds with that of Bavistan and antibacterial activity with that of Ampicillin, a β-lactam antibiotic.

Seeds of rice (*Oriza sativa*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and pea (*Pisum sativum*) were collected from local market. The assay seeds were sorted for uniformity of size and all damaged seeds were discarded. Before the bioassay seeds were washed with tap water and the surface were sterilized using NaCl (10%, v/v) for 10 min fol-

lowed by several washes in sterile distilled water. For testing phytotoxicity dehydrated ethanol was used as control. Bioassays were carried out using petridishes (90 mm diameter) containing a sheet of Whatman 1 filter paper as support. Test solutions (5 ml) was added to the filter paper in the petridish and dried completely *in vacuo* at 40 °C. Five seeds from each category were placed on the filter paper and incubated for 7 days at 25 °C in the dark. The effects of the pure compounds were determined by measuring the elongation of roots and average for each concentration.

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References

1. A. Mandal, A. Bothra, S. Ghosh and P. Ghosh, *European J. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **54**, 137.
2. P. Ghosh and A. Mandal, *Green Chemistry Letters and Reviews*, 2012, **5**, 127.
3. P. Ghosh and A. Mandal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 261.
4. P. Ghosh and A. Mandal, *Cat. Commun.*, 2011, **12**, 744.
5. P. Ghosh, Md. Golam Rasul, M. Chakraborty, A. Mandal and A. Saha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2011, **50B**, 1519.
6. P. Ghosh and P. Chakraborty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1037.
7. S. R. Dutta and B. P. Pradhan, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, **21B**, 575.
8. B. P. Pradhan and S. R. Dutta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1984, **23B**, 565.
9. S. R. Dutta and B. P. Pradhan, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1983, **22B**, 680.
10. B. P. Pradhan, P Ghosh and S. Chakraborty, *Indian J. Chem.*
11. V. Anjaneyulu and G. S. Rao, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1984, **23B**, 663.
12. L. Ruzicka, O. Jeger and P. Ringes, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, **27**, 972.
13. E. J. Corey and J. J. Ursprung, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5041.
14. B. P. Pradhan, S. Chakraborty, G. C. Subba and R. P. Sinha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1995, **34B**, 280.
15. P. Suleman, A. Al-Musallam and C. A. Menezes, *Biocontrol*, 2002, **47**, 207.
16. D. Saha, S. Dasgupta and A. Saha, *Pharma Biol.*, 2005, **43**, 87.